

Physiological Action of Anthraquinone-Containing Preparations

Authors : Dmitry Yu. Korulkin, Raissa A. Muzychkina, Evgenii N. Kojaev

Abstract : In review the generalized data about biological activity of anthraquinone-containing plants and specimens on their basis is presented. Data of traditional medicine, results of bioscreening and clinical researches of specimens are analyzed.

Keywords : anthraquinones, physiologically active substances, phytopreparation, Ramon

Conference Title : ICBBBE 2014 : International Conference on Biochemical, Biomolecular and Biopharmaceutical Engineering

Conference Location : Stockholm, Sweden

Conference Dates : July 14-15, 2014